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References

1. I. D. SHAH and J. P. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 889.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, 1961, p. 177.
3. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
4. K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. E. VDNKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **266**, 1927, 1011.
5. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
6. H. OLERUP, "Järnkloridernas Komplexitater (diss.)", *Lindstedts universitets-Bokhandel, Lund*, 1944.

A few benzylidene derivatives of N-substituted succinimides

D'COSTA ROSARIO AND V. V. NADKARNY*

Nadkarny Sacasa Research Laboratory,
Chemistry Department,
St. Xavier's College, Bombay-1.

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accepted 12 August 1975.

IN the Perkin's¹ Reaction, aromatic aldehydes condense with acid anhydrides possessing two hydrogen atoms on an α -carbon atom, in the presence of sodium acetate to give β -aryl acrylic acids. The reaction has been modified and condensations have been effected using aldehydes and carboxylic acids possessing α -hydrogen atoms. De Tar² used this procedure in the condensation of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde with phenylacetic acid, with triethylamine as

cinnimides were synthesized according to the method as given in Wild⁵.

The *N*-substituted imides, as obtained above were condensed with benzaldehyde, acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate for 4-5 hr under the conditions of Perkin's reaction to afford compounds of the type II.

All attempts to isolate cinnamic acid were unsuccessful. Earlier, a striking example had been cited where identical conditions were employed⁴.

A probable explanation is afforded as follows: Since the reaction is base-catalysed, the carbonion formed from *N*-substituted succinimide is secondary as compared to the formation of primary carbanion from acetic anhydride. Therefore the secondary carbanion is relatively less stable and more reactive, hence the product.

Similar condensations were effected using anisaldehyde to yield compounds of the type III.

The derivatives gave expected nitrogen analysis.

TABLE. DERIVATIVES OF THE TYPE II* AND III*

Compound	Mol. formula	m.p. °C
IIa	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	125°-6°
IIb	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	160°-1°
IIc	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	170°-1°
IIIa	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	136°
IIIb	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ NCl	165°-6°
IIIc	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ N	166°-7°

*(All the melting points are taken in a concentrated H₂SO₄ bath and may need further correction).

a = -phenyl. b = -*p*-chlorophenyl, c = -naphthyl

a base. The most significant applications¹ are: condensation of cyclic sulphur compounds such as rhodanine³ (containing active methylene groups) with aromatic aldehydes and the famous Erlenmeyer's azalactone synthesis.

N-Substituted succinimides contain active methylene groups and the aim of the present investigation is the extension of Perkin's reaction to these imides to form benzylidene derivatives. Therefore, *N*-phenyl-, *N*-*p*-chlorophenyl-, and *N*-naphthyl- suc-

Experimental procedure

A mixture of *N*-substituted succinimide (0.5 g) and aromatic aldehyde (0.6 g), acetic anhydride (2.5 ml) and fused sodium acetate (0.1 g), is refluxed at 170°-190° and maintained at that temperature for 4-5 hr. The reaction flask is then connected to steam distillation apparatus and excess of aldehyde is steam distilled. The resultant mixture, on cooling, affords long needles of the product which on crystallization

from alcohol-water gave reasonable yield (60-65%) of the compounds of the type II and III.

References

1. W. H. PERKIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1868, **21**, 53, 181; 1877 **31**, 388.
2. D. F. DE TAR, *Org. Synth.*, 1963, **4**, 730.
3. JULIAN and STURGIS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1126.
4. ERLÉNMEYER, *Ann.*, 1892, **164**, 271; 1904, **265**, 337; see also Plöchl, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2181.
5. F. Wild, *Charact. of Org. Compds.*, 2nd Edn. 1960, pp. 230.

Electrometric Studies of Rare Earth Complexes of *N*-Salicylideneorphanilic Acid

D. D. OZHA, B. R. SINGHVI AND R. K. MEHTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur.

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No work on the reactions of rare earth metals with *N*-salicylideneorphanilic acid (H_2SO) is reported in the existing literature. The present investigations are aimed at to determine the composition and stability constants of the La (III), Ce (III), Pr(III), Nd (III), Sm (III) and Gd (III) complexes

and stability constants of the complexes. For this purpose following solutions were titrated separately against 0.1M NaOH keeping, total volume as 40.0 ml (1) 10.0 ml. 0.01 M H_2SO +4.0 ml. 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +26.0 ml water, (2) 10.0 ml 0.01M H_2SO +4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +10.0 ml 0.01M $M(NO_3)_3$ +16.0 ml water, (3) 10.0 ml 0.01M H_2SO +4.0 ml 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +5.0 ml 0.01 M $M(NO_3)_3$ +21.0 ml water.

The mean values of dissociation constants (pK_1 & pK_2) as obtained by Algebraic method⁴ and Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values method have been found to be 2.05 and 8.13. The formation curves of the rare earth metal complexes representing $\bar{n}$ as a function of $-\log[A^{-2}]$ suggest the formation of 1:2 complex. Refinement of the approximate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was done by computational methods⁵ and the values obtained by all the methods are in fair agreement as shown in Table 1 in which the values of overall free energy changes at 25° are also included.

The stability of the complexes of the metals, having similar electronic configurations, increases with decreasing ionic size. This trend is also observed in the present case (Table 1) as the sequence of stability found is, La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm < Gd.

The rare earth complexes studied above have been isolated in the solid state by the method reported earlier.⁶ These compounds were analysed and their molecular weights and magnetic moments were determined. The results thus obtained are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Stability constants of trivalent metal complexes as H_2SO

Temperature = 25° ± 0.1°		$\mu = 0.1M NaClO_4$						
Metals		A	B	C	D	E	F	$-\Delta F$ K. Cal/mole
La(III)	log K_1	3.75	3.71	3.68	3.75	3.75	3.73	8.86
	log K_2	2.75	2.72	2.68	2.75	2.75	2.73	
Ce(III)	log K_1	4.26	4.22	4.20	4.26	4.26	4.24	10.77
	log K_2	3.63	3.60	3.57	3.63	3.63	3.61	
Pr(III)	log K_1	4.45	4.42	4.39	4.45	4.45	4.43	11.40
	log K_2	3.90	3.87	3.85	3.90	3.90	3.88	
Nd(III)	log K_1	5.12	5.10	5.07	5.11	5.12	5.10	12.96
	log K_2	4.36	4.32	4.30	4.37	4.36	4.34	
Sm(III)	log K_1	5.55	5.53	5.50	5.55	5.55	5.54	13.79
	log K_2	4.54	4.50	4.48	4.53	4.53	4.51	
Gd(III)	log K_1	5.81	5.78	5.75	5.81	5.80	5.79	14.33
	log K_2	4.66	4.63	4.61	4.66	4.68	4.65	

where A = Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values; B = Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values; C = Correction term; D = Successive approximation; E = Convergence formula; F = Average value; and $-\Delta F$ = Overall changes in free energy.

with *N*-salicylideneorphanilic acid (H_2SO). H_2SO was prepared by a general procedure as reported earlier¹.

Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{2,3} was followed to study the dissociation constants of H_2SO

The La(III) complex is found diamagnetic, as expected.

Considering elemental analyses, potentiometric, conductometric, and magnetic data it was found that